

EFFECTIVE METHODS OF DEVELOPING MEDIA COMPETENCES OF UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS

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Abstract

The article's goals are to assess students' media competency and investigate how it could develop within the context of higher education. The study's findings demonstrated that The responders are quite proud of their own degree of media proficiency. Students think about they are capable of making presentations, but more difficult tasks are scored in the in the intermediate range. It is reasonable to presume that the elements of the activities that are required for studying at a university exhibit better scores. Simultaneously, the abilities related to comprehensive examination of Information and the production of media goods are not given the same priority when planning instructional initiatives.

Keywords: media competence, media education, social media, students, higher education.

Introduction

The development of media education in modern conditions is caused by the influence of such factors as the dynamic penetration of digital technologies into all areas, growth of the volume and channels of information transmission. Young people today consume huge amounts of information that is posted on various platforms on the Internet, create and exchange electronic messages (Genedy, 2021: 30-36). This puts on the agenda the issues of the formation of media

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potential, as well as boosting the country's economy's competitiveness (Kamenev et al., 2019: 65-71).

New trends associated with an increase in the volume of information make special demands on the media competence of today's youth. Searching, reading, analyzing, understanding and interpreting information content are among the basic competencies required for work and study (Pereira, Moura, 2019: 678-689). In modern conditions «media competence includes not only the skills of using information technologies, the ability to navigate the Internet, but also the presence of a culture of media communication, interaction with other media users» (Konkov, 2019: 128).

As A. Fedorov, the media competence of an individual is a combination of his motives, knowledge, skills that contribute to the choice, use, critical analysis, assessment, creation and transmission of media texts (Fedorov, 2010: 64). Of particular interest is the indicators of the development of media competence developed by the scientist: motivational, contact, informational, perceptual, interpretive/evaluative, practical-operational, creative (Fedorov, 2013: 231-247).

Based on the analysis of in-depth media-biographical interviews with respondents of different age groups, factors were identified that prevent the negative influence of the media on the consciousness of individuals. These included the following: selective criticality, pragmatic trust and competence in the analysis of information, navigation through the news (Schwarzenegger, 2020: 361-377). These conclusions make it possible to single out the elements of a person's media competence, where the central link is criticality in the process of

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information consumption.

Conclusion

Despite the fact that modern students have basic skills in working with media, interpretive/evaluative and practical-operational competencies are insufficiently formed. The results of the study showed that students have a low assessment of the possibilities of forming media competence in the higher education system in the Russian Federation. On the one hand, the test system of knowledge control, focused on memorizing information, limits the possibilities of forming a pedagogical request for the development of students' research competencies. On the other hand, students pay attention to the need to modernize the approach to independent work of students in universities. It is required to strengthen the focus of attention on tasks that provide critical analysis of texts, interpretation of media content.

It can be assumed that the insufficient level of students' media competence is due to the absence of strict requirements in preparation for classes, the need to refer to primary sources, and to conduct a comparative analysis. An indirect confirmation of this conclusion is the insufficient amount of time that a modern student spends looking for information in preparation for classes. Promising areas in this context can be work with social networks, play, research and practice-oriented forms of educational activity. The focus of attention in organizing students' independent work should be shifted towards more complex activities, such as the preparation of infographics, analytical reports on statistical data, comparative analysis of media texts.

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References:

1. Al-Msie'deen et al., 2021 – Al-Msie'deen, R., Blasi, A.H., Alsuwaiket, M.A. (2021). Constructing a software requirements specification and design for electronic IT news magazine system. *International Journal of Advanced and Applied Sciences*. 8(11): 104-118. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.21833/ijaas.2021.11.014>
2. Al-Sawy, 2021 – Al-Sawy, Y.M. (2021). The role of electronic information resources in supporting scientific research at Northern Border University. *International Journal of Advanced and Applied Sciences*. 8(9): 43-49.
3. Banaji, Moreno-Almeida, 2021 – Banaji, S, Moreno-Almeida, C. (2021). Politicizing participatory culture at the margins: The significance of class, gender and online media for the practices of youth networks in the MENA region. *Global Media and Communication* 17(1):121-142. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1742766520982029>
4. Blokh, 2016 – Blokh, E.A. (2016). Sotsial'naya set' VKontakte kak faktor razvitiya mediakompetentsii podrostkov v ramkakh shkol'nogo press-tsentra [Social network VKontakte as a factor in the development of adolescents' media competence within the school press center]. *Mediasreda – Media Environment*. 11: 38-43. [in Russian]
5. Boronenko, T.A., Kaisina, A.V., Fedotova, V.S. (2017). Strategii mediaobrazovaniya: novye mediaformaty osveshcheniya rezul'tatov nauchno-issledovatel'skoi raboty studentov. [Media education strategies: new media

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formats for covering the results of students' research work]. Mediaobrazovanie – Media education. 3: 15-26. [in Russian]